

How bad are the growth hampering effects of non-communicable diseases? The case of developing countries

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Abstract: This paper attempts to estimate the impact of Non-Communicable Diseases on economic growth in developing countries. In fact, the literature has confirmed the existence of causal liaisons between the epidemiological burden of diseases and macroeconomic aspects. This analysis is conducted through a dynamic panel of 29 middle-income countries around the Mediterranean basin and Central Asia over the period between 1995 and 2016 using the System Generalized Method of Moments (SGMM) to account for the potential endogeneity of the explanatory variables. The robustness and consistence of the estimates was verified by statistical tests and by the estimation of alternative versions of the basic specification.

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1. Introduction

In the midst of the epidemiological transition and the subsequent global changes in lifestyle and nutritional habits, the emergence of non-communicable diseases have shifted trends of morbidity and mortality. Currently, non-communicable diseases (NCDs henceforth) claim more lives than all of the other causes of death combined, especially in developing countries where 48% of the mortality burden occurs (World Health Organization, 2014).

The economic costs associated with NCDs' mortality and morbidity go beyond health care costs to the hindering of technological potential and physical capital accumulation. In fact, the literature has widely discussed causal channels by which health affects macroeconomic performances, as well as the analytical frameworks that allow quantifying the magnitude of health aspects' impacts on economic features, as will be discussed further below.

This paper aims to explore the impact of the mortality burden of non-communicable diseases on economic growth in developing countries through the estimation of a dynamic panel data model on a sample of 29 middle-income countries from Europe, Central Asia, the Middle East and North Africa, over a period of 22 years between 1995 and 2016.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 discusses the literature related to the epidemiology and economics of chronic diseases. Next we define our

model as well as the estimation procedure in section 3. Finally, the results are reported and discussed in sections 4 and 5.

2. Literature review

2.1. Epidemiological transition

The worldwide shifts in morbidity and mortality trends and the resulting emergence of non-communicable diseases known as the epidemiological transition is a consequence of complex demographic, economic and social factors (Omran, 1971; Friis & Sellers, 2014). These factors include improvements in life expectancy, globalization of nutritional habits, and the subsequent propagation of obesity and hypertension (Blacher, Levy, Mourad, Safar, & Bakris, 2016; Boccia, Villari, & Ricciardi, 2015; Franco, Cooper, Bilal, & Fuster, 2011).

Currently, non-communicable diseases, especially cardiovascular diseases (CVDs henceforth), stroke, diabetes and cancer are the leading cause of mortality and disability worldwide (World Health Organization, 2014). In fact, the change of focus from infectious to non-communicable diseases and the development of the concept of risk factors is one of the main scientific contribution of the -still ongoing- Framingham cohort study, which aims to reveal hidden cases of cardiovascular disease among healthy subjects, over extensive periods (Aschengrau & Seage, 2013).

Although the epidemiological transition is a global phenomenon, the propagation trends of NCDs show wide dissimilarities across countries at different development stages. In fact, developed countries are placed at the late stages of the epidemiological transition, characterized by a drastic decrease in infectious diseases and a control of the dynamic of NCDs. In contrast, some developing countries still struggle with the double-burden problem, where the burden of both infectious and non-infectious is quite important (Franco et al., 2011). Furthermore, the consequences of the double-burden problem are exacerbated in Sub-Saharan African countries (Mensah, 2013), where health systems are weak and their ability to deal with complex economic and financial challenges is limited (Franco et al., 2011).

2.2. Subsection

The literature has explored the causal channels by which health acts upon economic features. In fact, the epidemiological burden of NCDs affects macroeconomic performances through the channel of labor market and the channel of health expenditures and capital accumulation.

According to Bloom, Cafiero-Fonseca, McGovern, Prettner, Stanciole et al. (2014) Non-Communicable Diseases (NCDs) affect the economic growth through many causal channels. In fact, they argue that disability and early mortality caused by NCDs reduce labor supply and labor productivity due to early retirement. This was in line with (Keogh-Brown, Jensen, Arrighi, & Smith, 2016) which analyzed the impact of Alzheimer's Disease (AD henceforth) on the Chinese economy. Their analysis estimated that labor-supply-decreasing effects of dementia would account for 10% of the global economic effect of the disease. In fact, the authors argued that the labor-supply-decreasing effect of AD is

not strictly associated with patients but also with informal caregivers, which accounts for 34% of the global effect on the labor market, as for patient-specific labor effects only account for 28%. Similarly, cardiovascular diseases would have costed the Russian Federation the loss of 2.1 million working years in 2006 and 1.7 million in 2009, which sum to a total cost of €24.5 billion in 2006 and €24.4 billion in 2009 (Kontsevaya, Kalinina, & Oganov, 2013).

Accordingly, the disability and early mortality due to NCDs would widen inequalities and cause the poverty spiral (Abegunde & Stanciole, 2006) where individuals are deprived of their productive potential which would, ultimately, reduce income and savings. In addition, NCDs burden would impact foreign capital influx due to diminishing labor productivity and access to factors of production as well as decreasing investment in physical and human capital caused by increased consumption. The aggregate effect of these factors would contribute to the worsening of social inequalities and the deepening of poverty. However, good health would improve labor productivity and would free resources to be invested in non-health sectors (Abegunde & Stanciole, 2006; Mensah, 2013).

In addition, the epidemiological burden of NCDs would hinder human and physical capital accumulation. Chronic diseases patients would be pushed out of the labor force, thus affecting lifetime expectations and the social rate of time preference, as well as non-health demand (Abegunde & Stanciole, 2006). Moreover, health expenditures associated with NCDs burden would negatively affect savings at both the individual and the State levels, which would force the government to raise tax rates in order to meet increased spending and potentially divert public investment away from targeting strategic sectors (Bloom et al., 2014).

2.3. Analytical frameworks

The exploring of the causal relationships between health aspects and the macroeconomy has raised methodological debates among health economists over the choice of analytical frameworks and the variables that could be used to approach health. The choice of an empirical framework depends on a tradeoff between its ability to replicate data trends and satisfactory underlying theoretical foundations.

The estimation of the economic impact of health could be conducted either through an economic growth perspective (Abegunde & Stanciole, 2006; Bloom et al., 2014), Cost-of-Illness method (Kontsevaya et al., 2013), or through general equilibrium approach (Keogh-Brown et al., 2016; Verikios, Dixon, Rimmer, & Harris, 2015). In this study, we adopt a growth model framework to capture the effect of disease on economic growth through the channels of production factors.

3. Method

3.1. Data

The statistical analysis was conducted through a sample of 29 middle-income countries from Middle East, North Africa, Europe and Central Asia over the period between 1995 and 2016.

The dataset used in the analysis was retrieved from the World Development Indicators database offered by the World Bank as well as the Global Health Data Exchange dataset offered by the Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation (IHME).

At a first glance, the variable associated with mortality due to NCDs seems to be highly correlated (85.91%) with aggregate income, and health expenditures per capita would be correlated with life expectancy by 62.11%. Furthermore, the analysis of the within and between variances highlighted the predominance of the between variability.

3.2. Model

In order to empirically assess the impact of chronic diseases mortality burden on economic growth was conducted via a dynamic panel data model. Thus, we apply the following model:

$$y_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 \cdot y_{i,t-1} + \beta_2 \cdot ncd + \sum_{j=1}^k \delta_j \cdot x_{it} + \eta_i + \varepsilon_{it}; \quad (1)$$

$$i = 1 \dots n; t = 1 \dots T; j = 1 \dots k$$

Where y is the logarithm of aggregate income, ncd is the logarithm of NCDs mortality in working age, and x is the vector of control variables, namely gross fixed capital formation and the labor force, all expressed in natural logarithms.

The model was estimated using the System Generalized Method of Moments (SGMM), due to the potential existence of endogenous variables in the model. The latter being autoregressive would induce a correlation with the idiosyncratic error, which would cause the non-convergence of usual estimators. In fact, applying the within estimator would underestimate the coefficients in small samples (Nickell, 1981).

Consequently, the Generalized Method of Moments stood out as a reliable mean to overcome variable endogeneity. In this paper, we use the System Generalized Method of Moments developed by Blundell & Bond (1998) as a response to the weak instrument problem that encountered the Generalized Method of Moments estimator developed by Arellano & Bond (1991).

4. Results

In the principal specification, we assumed lagged aggregate income and gross fixed capital formation to be predetermined.

We included second and third lag as instruments for lagged aggregate income in the level equation, and the first and the second lag in the difference equation. As for gross fixed capital formation, we used the second and the third lag as instruments in both level and difference equations.

For the sake of comparison, we estimated various versions of the model. The first and second specifications were estimated using the two-step system GMM, where the variable related to NCDs mortality is assumed to be exogenous in the first specification and endogenous in the second one. In the third version, we used the difference GMM estimator, and the one-step GMM estimator in the fourth. These alternative estimates confirmed to significance of explanatory variables. In addition, we have estimated static versions of the model using the within and the Generalized Least Squares estimators. Table 1 and table 2 report the different estimates.

As a result, all the coefficients have showed significant values at 5% significance level. Our variable of interest showed significant negative effect upon aggregate income. In fact, a 1% increase in the mortality rate of Non-Communicable Diseases would result in a 0.21% decrease in aggregate income. Surprisingly, the fertility rate exhibits a negative coefficient that is significant at the significance level of 1%, it would affect aggregate income by -0.28%, which is not consistent with the findings of Suhrcke & Urban (2010) who used a similar approach.

The fixed and random effects model reported the same tendencies. The fixed effects model estimation showed that a 1% increase in NCDs mortality would result in a decrease of aggregate income by 0.23, and the random effects model showed that an increase in mortality rate by the same proportion across time and between countries would result in average decrease in aggregate income by 0.21%.

TABLE 1. DYNAMIC MODEL ESTIMATES

	TWO-STEP SYSTEM GMM ESTIMATOR RESULTS	TWO-STEP SYSTEM GMM ESTIMATION WHERE NCDs MORTALITY ASSUMED TO BE ENDOGENOUS	TWO-STEP DIFFERENCE GMM	ONE-STEP SYSTEM GMM
<i>LAGGED AGGREGATE INCOME</i>	0.724*** (0.058) [0.604 ; 0.843]	0.736*** (0.050) [0.630 ; 0.842]	0.763*** (0.086) [0.585 ; 0.942]	0.733*** (0.016) [0.700 ; 0.765]
<i>NCDs MORTALITY</i>	-0.210*** (0.073) [-0.362 ; -0.058]	-0.283*** (0.091) [-0.477 ; -0.089]	-0.100** (0.041) [-0.185 ; -0.015]	-0.238*** (0.021) [-0.280 ; -0.196]
<i>FERTILITY RATE</i>	-0.287*** (0.082) [-0.457 ; -0.116]	-0.224*** (0.052) [-0.336 ; -0.113]	-0.219*** (0.039) [-0.300 ; -0.137]	-0.217*** (0.020) [-0.257 ; -0.178]
<i>LABOR FORCE</i>	0.457*** (0.103) [0.245 ; 0.669]	0.495*** (0.108) [0.266 ; 0.725]	0.141** (0.067) [0.002 ; 0.279]	0.441*** (0.033) [0.374 ; 0.508]
<i>GROSS FIXED CAPITAL FORMATION</i>	0.0825** (0.035) [0.008 ; 0.156]	0.0977*** (0.032) [0.029 ; 0.165]	0.156** (0.063) [0.025 ; 0.286]	0.104*** (0.010) [0.083 ; 0.125]
AR(1) test	0.006***	0.002***	0.002***	0.000***
AR(2) test	0.219	0.153	0.263	0.199
Hansen test	0.195	0.186	0.183	

Note: *, **, *** - denote significance level at the 10%, 5% and 1%. Standard error reported in parentheses. Confidence intervals reported in accolades.

TABLE 2. STATIC MODEL ESTIMATES

	FIXED EFFECTS	RANDOM EFFECTS
<i>NCDs MORTALITY</i>	-0.233*** (0.079) [-0.390 ; -0.077]	-0.213*** (0.064) [-0.3388 ; -0.087]
<i>FERTILITY RATE</i>	-0.050 (0.0592) [-0.166 ; 0.065]	-0.119** (0.051) [-0.220 ; -0.01]
<i>LABOR FORCE</i>	0.902*** (0.080) [0.743 ; 1.061]	0.815*** (0.070) [0.677 ; 0.952]
<i>GROSS FIXED CAPITAL FORMATION</i>	0.477*** (0.0142) [0.449 ; 0.505]	0.495*** (0.013) [0.467 ; 0.522]
R ² Within	0.833	0.833
Between	0.962	0.969
Overall	0.961	0.967
F-Statistic		0.00***
Hausman test (<i>p</i> -value)		0.792

Note: *, **, *** - denote significance level at the 10%, 5% and 1%. Standard error reported in parentheses. Confidence intervals reported in accolades.

5. Discussion

Our findings suggested that a 1% increase in mortality rate due to NCDs among working age people would cost developing countries composing our sample an average annual decrease of aggregate output of 0.21%, which amounts to an average loss of PPP\$ 69.9 billion. This finding is consistent with research focalized on the topic. In fact, NCDs have been expected to cost an output loss of 0.48% for Brazil, 1.18% for China, 1.27% for India, 0.65% for Nigeria, and 5.34% for Russia. Comparatively, Suhrcke & Urban (2010) estimated the impact of cardiovascular diseases on economic growth using the same methodology and argued that these diseases hinder economic growth of developed countries by lowering per capita output by 0.069%. However, their findings rejected the assumption that CVDs affect economic growth in developing countries, which conflicts with the findings described in this paper. We note that the statistical findings depend largely on the proxy variables used to approach the disease burden as well as the development stage at which the analyzed countries are placed.

According to this comparative analysis, the economic loss associated with NCDs is quite considerable, especially for developing countries striving to join emerging and developed countries. An important economic burden of disease would hinder the productivity of the workforce, thus affecting the country attractiveness vis-à-vis foreign capital inflows, that relies essentially on the abundance and affordability of the labor force (Fischer, 1998).

In sum, this paper attempted to assess the global economic growth related effects of NCDs on developing countries around the Mediterranean basin and from Central Asia.

However, it fails to evaluate the contribution of each NCD to the economic burden as well as the contribution of each causal channel in the global macroeconomic effect. Filling these methodological gaps as well as extending the reasoning to include burden reducing policy simulation would be subject of future research.

6. Conclusions

In this paper, we attempted to estimate the joint effect of Non-Communicable Diseases on aggregate output of 29 middle-income countries from around the Mediterranean basin and Central Asia over a period of 22 years. The findings suggested the existence of a negative effect of NCDs working age mortality on the efficiency of aggregate production.

Correspondingly, Morocco would also be subject to development-hampering effects of Non-Communicable Diseases that would diminish the country's technology potential and possibly worsen the situation known as "moderate growth trap" that the Moroccan economy struggles to get out of (Agenor & El Aynaoui, 2015).

Thus, the establishment of a public health intelligence program that is based on the systematic and continuous process of collecting, consolidating, analyzing and disseminating health data in a reliable, flexible and efficient fashion would be able to provide relevant health information to health policymakers (Regmi & Gee, 2016).

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